

ARCTIC PASSION

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Strengthening European capabilities

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Content

Strengthening European capabilities	4
Visibility of the Arctic	4
Google Search trends to reveal Arctic visibility in relation to other topics	4
Visibility of Copernicus services	7
Comparing Copernicus offer to US and Finnish sites	7
Comparison within European sites	8
Use of Copernicus services	10
Distribution of interest and linking	10
Data dissemination sites	11
Marine service site Ubersuggest analysis	13
Arctic Passion services and State of the Arctic	15
Pilot Service example: Lake ice service as a single service site analysis	15
Promotion without marketing budgets	16
Conclusions to Strengthening European capabilities	18
ANNEX	19

Strengthening European capabilities

The initial purpose of this report was to examine the success of the 'Arctic window of Copernicus' site, which our project was initiating. This plan was for this platform to serve as a point-of-access to all the outputs from the Pilot Services as well as providing access to Arctic relevant observations, data, and products. However, the Copernicus services developed a more extensive portal called the [Arctic Hub portal](https://www.arctic.hub.copernicus.eu/) (<https://www.arctic.hub.copernicus.eu/>) as an independent effort. Following discussions with commission representatives and the responsible institute for the Copernicus Arctic Hub (Mercator Ocean International: MOI), it was decided that we should avoid duplication. Consequently, the Arctic PASSION's Arctic Window of Copernicus would not be implemented. Instead, Arctic PASSION was tasked with providing guidance and recommendations for the Copernicus Arctic Hub (Deliverable D2.8 'Arctic Window of Copernicus - The Arctic PASSION perspective'). As a consequence, the current deliverable D8.3 has been appropriately modified, we will now concentrate on the visibility of the Arctic in global internet usage and how Copernicus and Arctic Passion services have raised internet awareness.

Visibility of the Arctic

The internet, and particularly web browsing technology, has solidified itself as the foundation of almost all information related activities, provision or consumption. For context, we first look at how much web traffic there is overall. Tracking the traffic on the internet is technically feasible and the most common interface to websites has become the Google search engine. Google is visited by over 700 million unique visitors with over 32 billion visits in March 2025. According to Similarweb, it represents almost 18 % of all internet traffic and combined with Youtube, Google is involved in 30% of all web traffic (see Figure 1). The next three sites combined traffic represent together only 5,6 %, so analysis of Google is a very strong indicator of global visibility and interest. How does the Arctic as a topic and Copernicus as an offer show up in this interaction of services and end users.

	Domain (10,000)	Traffic Share ↓	MoM traffic change	Country Rank	Monthly Visits	Unique Visitors	Visit Duration	Pages/Visit
1		↑ 9.52%	#1	32.24B	710.7M	00:16:49	12.41	
2		↑ 10.55%	#2	22.20B	542.4M	00:23:44	15.07	
3		↑ 9.66%	#3	5.527B	310.2M	00:15:07	19.36	
4		↑ 6.47%	#10	3.460B	205.6M	00:14:27	4.17	
5		↑ 16.40%	#8	2.850B	197.2M	00:06:11	3.47	

Figure 1 Overall leaders of website traffic globally. (similarweb.com accessed 29.4.2025)

Google Search trends to reveal Arctic visibility in relation to other topics

Google offers a Trends service for free (trends.google.com), which allows you to investigate the google.com search terms, topics and news articles in particular. Comparing search terms relevant to the Arctic Passion project: 'European Union', 'Arctic', 'observation', 'remote sensing', 'sea ice' and so on, one can see the trends over the last 5 years. These are displayed in Figure 2.

Overall web searches of 'Arctic' and 'observation' are higher compared to the European Union, but the Russian invasion of Ukraine on 21st February 2022, spiked the European Union especially in news

searches above searches about the 'Arctic'. While there is little trend in overall searches of the word 'Arctic', the interest in news about the Arctic seems to be increasing between 2020 and 2025. 'Observation', 'sea ice' and 'remote sensing' pop up infrequently, while the 'European Union' is more associated with news items than the general interest of internet users.

One can also choose a category of searches, which adds context to the search term. In science category searches 'observation', 'sea ice' and 'remote sensing' clearly get more prominent compared to science related questions for the 'European Union'.

All in all, results from Google searched suggest that the Arctic is a topic of significant interest to people from all around the world, as is visualized in Figure 3. Also, Greenland and Svalbard would be dark red, but we chose to use the drawing option that excludes small regions. Small samples tend to have much bigger interests in certain topics and the Arctic and Greenland or Svalbard with small communities is a perfect example. Here the topic is so much searched that it would expand the scales of proportional interest and weaken the difference elsewhere. The colour scale in the graph is based on relative importance in a country. Interestingly, the people from non-Arctic nations, like Australia and China for example, show large interest in search the 'Arctic' topic.

Figure 2 Trends.google.com statistics for the last 5 years for search terms European Union, arctic, observation, remote sensing and sea ice. Above the web searches, news searches in the middle and below web searches categorized as science related. (site capture accessed 29.4.2025)

Figure 3 Distribution of interest by region for arctic search term highlighting with deeper reds stronger regional interest in the map. Top 5 related queries with arctic in it on the right (trends.google.com accessed 29.4.2025)

Visibility of Copernicus services

Copernicus services are for the most part web services, with only a few exceptions in security and emergency management domains. This makes analysing Copernicus visibility simple, because we can analyse the visibility via internet traffic to the service websites. Compared to tracking visibility in TV or newspaper media, this also allows much more detailed information on where the user comes from and the depth of the engagement. There are excellent tools to analyse website performance looking at general visits, user engagement and background, for example where the visits come from. These services help to identify competitors, as well as comparing the placing of key search words and the planning of marketing.

The market leader for data that is collected from heavy traffic internet switches around the world is [similarweb.com](https://www.similarweb.com). With a free account one can compare and analyse up to 5 different domains/sites with limitations to the details and how many queries one gets to do per day. The free access is enough to provide a good understanding of unique visits as a proxy for Copernicus services visibility which can be compared to similar other services.

Comparing Copernicus offer to US and Finnish sites

See below in Figure 4, the visits and engagement comparison between the Arctic Hub, the Copernicus EO data service dataspace.copernicus.eu, its alternative WEKEO, the US National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) and the Finnish Meteorological Institutes (FMI) website. By doing this analysis one can understand the difference between a near-real-time updated service like a popular national weather service and data dissemination sites which are more targeting expert users.

It also highlights that in the month of March 2025, only 57 visits happened to the Arctic Hub. This is important knowledge as it shows that marketing is needed to make the Arctic Hub visible and impactful to the broader stakeholder community. The NSIDC had almost 400,000 visits in March 2025. On the

other hand, general purpose weather information in a country of a population of 5,5 million is about 20 times more popular than satellite imagery and other EO data products globally. The popularity is of course significantly less than the overall internet tops Google and Meta with Google Search, Youtube, Facebook and Instagram making the top 4 globally in March 2025. The popularity of a site is of course also determined by a mission for it and how well that resonates with peoples' interests. So with the Arctic Hub maybe not being so clear on what it should achieve, the content can't be formed as usefully.

To make sense of this information, one must go beyond looking simply at a person visiting a website and look at how long they are staying and how many different pages they look at during a visit on average. Here one can highlight that the Copernicus dataspace site is in fact generating more page views in total for March than the Finnish weather service and a visit is taking generally seven and a half minutes compared to the under two minutes visit of Finns to know what they are facing outside. Long visits and many pages may mean that it is not easy to find what one is looking for. So, website analysis is not straightforward, but especially as continuous practice, tracking one's internet following, helps to make more impact.

Figure 4 website performance comparison between Copernicus Arctic Hub, DataSpace, US national snow and ice data center, WEKEO and Finnish Meteorological Institute domains and sites. (similarweb.com accessed 25.4.2025)

Comparison within European sites

For Figure 5, the NSIDC and WEKEO domains are exchanged for the total Copernicus.eu presence in order to understand how a European commercial offering is doing with the Sentinel-hub.com service provided by a Slovenian company. The ranking globally, and in the US, shows how interest is very much dispersed on a national level, with few brands having global reach. Copernicus and Sentinel-hub seem to have managed to penetrate the US market, because the ranks in this highly competitive market are close to the global results. The FMI (Ilmatieteenlaitos.fi) site shows how a global rank which is based

mainly on a very strong following in one country translates to a decent global result but has no relevance in another country. Especially for those that are not familiar with the language of Finland. Browsing is nowadays also strongly divided between desktop and mobile devices. More mobile devices are more active overall but longer visits usually are made on desktop devices.

Figure 5 Comparing global, US and Industry ranks for Copernicus Arctic Hub, CDSE, FMI, Copernicus domain overall and Sentinel-Hub. (similarweb.com accessed 25.4.2025)

The geographical information can be highlighted as shown in Figure 6. The orange Copernicus CDSE is the leading target in most countries, with the total traffic being analysed. All traffic means that transfers of large files are counted in their total size and outweigh the many smaller transfers of a web service optimized for speedy page views by many users. This explains why in Finland the Copernicus dataspace has more traffic than the national weather service with hundreds of thousands of visits per day, but small compared to the large transfers of data. Looking at the percentages the United States accruing almost 22% of all traffic is very likely less than all European countries combined.

Figure 6 Geographical distribution of visits for the same sites as in figure 2. FMI is green, CDSE orange, Copernicus.eu yellow and Sentinel-hub blue. Only the top 20 countries are displayed with only 5 named, as disclosing all countries requires a paid service. (similarweb.com accessed 25.4.2025)

This figure is known from Copernicus' own web traffic monitoring reports.

Figure 7 Comparison of site performance for Copernicus services Dataspace, Climate, Atmosphere, Land and Emergency. (similarweb.com accessed 26.4.2025)

searches or web ads are not being used.

Use of Copernicus services

Moving on to analyse more particularly the Copernicus services. For the amount of organic (means direct or via links) visits, we excluded the Marine and the Security services, based on their clearly lower numbers from the similarweb comparison. The Marine service is separately analysed with a service called Ubersuggest after the comparison.

Climate Change service is almost as popular as Dataspace with over half a million visits in March, but with longer visits on average, over 12 minutes. To achieve these longer views the information is deemed to be interesting to users. Also, the other three services with over 100,000 or 200,000 visits have a significant following, but there is room for improvement. Another striking difference in Figure 7 is the average time spent at the other services sites, which is clearly less.

Distribution of interest and linking

Origin-wise China is topping the single country traffic statistics, with US, India and Indonesia showing the huge global interest in Copernicus services. With Italy, as the March 2025, being top European country. If we take the European Union as a whole, with almost 30 countries, it would surpass China as the largest traffic destination. Europe Union accounts for over 40% of Copernicus usage.

The channels graph (figure x) is important as it very shows that Copernicus services do not use internet marketing. Basically, all traffic is either users directly choosing the sites or organically meaning unpaid search engine traffic. Some referrals as in links from other sites and a quite small amount of social media traffic. Paid

Figure 8 Social media based traffic to Copernicus services.

Figure 8, shows social traffic which means traffic that comes from user posted links to the services on Youtube, Reddit, Facebook, LinkedIn or others. Dataspace has significant traffic from Youtube links and the Emergency services from several social media sites, foremost LinkedIn.

Figure 9 Referrals as in links on other sites to Copernicus services.

Referrals to Copernicus services (Figure 9) are dominated by the traffic that Sentinel-Hub is generating to the Dataspace service, hinting at a possible technical solution where some Sentinel-Hub material in fact is sourced from Dataspace. So, a Sentinel-Hub page request also generates direct traffic to the Dataspace service.

CSDN.net seems to be an important source of information for Chinese developers, with a lot of links to Copernicus services. ChatGPT seems to use the Climate Change service a lot for its augmented answers, which tells about true interest and useful information at C3S. Crawler traffic is excluded from this analysis, but report [from end of 2024](#) estimated it to be 28 percent of all web traffic. The referred chatgpt traffic in figure 9 is the one that is generated by people following the links that ChatGPT provides in its answers.

Data dissemination sites

Figure 10 Data subdomains for Land, Climate, Atmosphere, Emergency and Marine Copernicus services. (similarweb.com accessed 27.4.2025)

Figure 10 displays the data dissemination services subdomains usage. Here the marine services is included in place of Land service (which uses Dataspace for its dissemination). The Atmosphere and Emergency services are clearly less attractive on the data side than in news and report-like content. For Emergency, one must account for the Emergency Warnings Data service (EWDS) being only a part of the data offering, where the other data is integrated on the main site. The Marine service is stronger on the data side than overall, but one cannot directly compare Similarweb estimates to the ones from Ubersuggest. Both services use samples from a select set of internet switches and estimate from these a total global statistic mathematically. The time window is slightly different as Similarweb is March

and Ubersuggest the last 30 days. Climate and Dataspace services show that their most attractive offering is the data available.

There is also a clear improvement in the time spent on the sites for the data dissemination compared to the average overall then comparing the visit duration here to Figure 7 - all durations improved significantly.

Figure 11 show the browsing and searching habits of Copernicus service visitors. First of the word cloud of the topics (based on searches made and other sites visited) reveals that science use is strong. Below the top 50 sites are listed that Copernicus users also used in order of generated traffic. Again, only the top 5 sites are named, the next 45 sites may be guessed based on the category and traffic shares of the sites. The users are not very special based on this data. Maybe their Google services usage is higher and Facebook or Instagram usage lower than for overall web users. Else there are little insights to be gained. Of course, the top site being Sentinel-Hub is testament to how collaboration in the Earth Observation domain is probably very beneficial for both parties and we could build out more this reliance on each other.

Marine service site Ubersuggest analysis

Next, we will look at the Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service with Ubersuggest analysis. With lower traffic sites, one can get more analysis for free, just registering with these websites support services all trying to help with Search Engine Optimization (SEO) as a very large portion of web traffic is directed by search engines.

Google Search Engine can be queried for the keywords leading to a site and Figure 12 shows a selection of keywords that point to the Marine service. The volume of this statistic estimates the number of searches in the last 30 days, while the position explains if the Marine service page was first or a later result offered. This position directly relates to the SEO difficulty, with difficult ones suggesting to use paid results to overtake earlier results. Maybe even other actors paid results are the reason for a lower position. In general, the positions are good as the top 10 gets to the first page which almost all users tend to find their links to jump to from.

Figure 13 shows which other sites answer similar keywords. This statistic is based on UK English sites and UK traffic, so it is not surprising that one of the biggest sites in the UK is also the main competition for Marine service keyword – the BBC. This is a

Figure 11 What else are Copernicus service users browsing and what keywords do they search for. Top 50 sites shown. (similarweb.com accessed 25.4.2025)

global heavyweight at 346 million visits in 30 days compared to the 38 thousands registered at Ubersuggest. The 10,000 times bigger reach suggests that Copernicus services should enhance collaboration with European media to improve their reach. C3S has had a collaboration with Euronews, which is one of the reasons behind the C3S success compared to the other Copernicus services. The Guardian as another media company in the top 5 similar sites is pointing also to this and their 78 million visits in 30 days are also still 200 times more than C3S is getting.

LOCATIONS		GB / EN [1,617]	ES / ES [4,471]	US / EN [4,126]	FR / FR [2,467]	MORE
KEYWORDS	VOLUME	POSITION	EST. VISITS	SEO DIFFICULTY		
atlantic sea temperature marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/ocean-visualisation-tools/atlantic-...	320	1	95	46 (6 Months ago)	Search Results	
atlantic ocean temperature marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/ocean-visualisation-tools/atlantic-...	320	1	95	33 (Over 6 months)	Search Results	
ocean current marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/ocean-currents	6,600	9	90	67 (1 Week ago)	Search Results	
marine currents marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/ocean-currents	6,600	7	89	22 (Over 6 months)	Search Results	
green ocean marine.copernicus.eu/services/the-green-ocean	170	1	81	19 (Over 6 months)	Search Results	
currents ocean marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/ocean-currents	6,600	10	69	30 (Over 6 months)	Search Results	
water salinity marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/ocean-visualisation-tools/baltic-se...	3,600	10	61	59 (2 Weeks ago)	Search Results	
cmems marine.copernicus.eu/	140	1	56	29 (Over 6 months)	Search Results	
ocean and ocean currents marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/ocean-currents	6,600	8	42	40 (Over 6 months)	Search Results	
currents in the ocean marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/ocean-currents	6,600	9	42	25 (Over 6 months)	Search Results	
myocean marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/myocean-viewer	260	3	30	1 (6 Months ago)	Search Results	

Figure 12 Keywords pointing to the Marine service on Google Search with statistics for the United Kingdom English (Ubersuggest, accessed 26.4.2025).

Other sites can be viewed as natural similar sites as these are international partners like the US NASA or partners/subcontractors like the UK MetOffice. Europa.EU is referring to all European Union institutions on the internet like the Commission, the EU Parliament and EU agencies. This lot is probably using the data and information provided by the Marine Services, so this is the most natural similar site and in fact a testament of success in Copernicus.

SIMILAR WEBSITES	COMMON KEYWORDS	KEYWORDS GAP	ESTIMATED TRAFFIC	BACKLINKS
bbc.co.uk	518 View All	6.9m View All	314.5m	0.5b
europa.eu	478 View All	995,615 View All	2.2m	1.7b
nasa.gov	432 View All	381,386 View All	14.0m	379.2m
metoffice.gov.uk	301 View All	600,634 View All	17.4m	24.9m
theguardian.com	297 View All	4.4m View All	78.5m	293.7m

Figure 13 Similar websites based on similar keywords being present on the site. The data is compared for English content in the United Kingdom. (Ubersuggest accessed 26.4.2025)

Another interesting analysis can be done by looking in a particular language/market scope for pages that attracted more visits. This data is displayed in Figure 14. Popular pages inspire other sites to link to them, and the amount of these backlinks is displayed along the estimated visits. To the right these

backlinks are tracked for popular discussion social media sites Facebook, Pinterest and Reddit. Except for the Marine services frontpage, there are only a few backlinks, and even the frontpage is only 25 times linked to from Facebook. The other discussion sites have zero links to any pages on the Marine service site. It seems clear that Copernicus services should seek to organise more discussion on these sites, especially on Reddit and Pinterest. Unfortunately, Ubersuggest was not tracking LinkedIn, which might in this more professional context be more the place for discussions about the Copernicus Marine services. But Facebook in particular, has been used for spreading misinformation via paid content in many cases and combating that with quality assured information requires a level playing field.

TOP PAGES BY COUNTRY				US / EN [4,126]	ES / ES [4,471]	FR / FR [2,467]	IT / IT [2,151]	MORE
SEO TITLE URL	EST. VISITS	BACKLINKS	f	p	r			
Atlantic Ocean Temperature CMEMS marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/ocean-visualisation-tools/atlantic-ocean-temperat...	2,153 View All	3 View All	0	0	0			
Monitoring the Congo river discharge - Africa continent marine.copernicus.eu/services/user-learning-services/monitoring-congo-river-discha...	214 View All	2 View All	0	0	0			
Baltic Sea Salinity CMEMS marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/ocean-visualisation-tools/baltic-sea-salinity	196 View All	2 View All	0	0	0			
Copernicus Marine Service marine.copernicus.eu/	138 View All	223,787 View All	25	0	0			
Water Reservoir CMEMS marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/water-reservoir	84 View All	3 View All	0	0	0			
Touring Europe's coasts: water quality and flooding in Venice marine.copernicus.eu/news/water-quality-flooding-venice	83 View All	2 View All	0	0	0			
The Green Ocean CMEMS marine.copernicus.eu/services/the-green-ocean	72 View All	2 View All	0	0	0			
Ocean Waves CMEMS marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/ocean-waves	67 View All	2 View All	0	0	0			
Ocean Currents CMEMS marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/ocean-currents	66 View All	0 View All	0	0	0			
Weather and Climate CMEMS marine.copernicus.eu/explainers/why-ocean-important/weather-and-climate	55 View All	0 View All	0	0	0			

Figure 14 Top pages by country is highlighting often visited pages, how many backlinks they have attracted and if any of these are on social media and public discussion sites like Facebook, Pinterest or Reddit.

Arctic Passion services

All Arctic Passion services are public free for anyone to use services which don't require registration or hinder any usage of valuable information in them. However, the analysis we have displayed previously in this report cannot be used for them, because as fresh or not yet finished sites the visits to them are too few to allow a global analysis like Similarweb or even Ubersuggest. With only tens or hundreds of visits per month, this is not enough to make statistically significant conclusions from global sampling. This applies also to the Arcticpassion.eu site and sites from predecessor or parallel projects. Similarweb recorded 107 visits to the project site in March.

Pilot Service example: Lake ice service as a single service site analysis

Here we would need to look at data collected at the server by the operators themselves. This exercise was performed in WP5 for the lake ice service and tried for the permafrost by Arctic PASSION partner Spatino. The lake ice services is a EO-based information service if lakes are covered in ice. It initially was developed for Finland, but has been extended to the northern hemisphere. For the lake ice service, the exercise based on the web servers' usage statistics yielded a good analysis of where the end users

are coming from, but compared to Google Analytics like services, the details for contacting users are limited. D5.3 Pilot Services Impact Assessments and Generalization has evaluated the societal benefit of this service with even more details being available in Isabel Donners Master thesis '[Assessing Societal Benefits and Economic Impacts of earth observation data in the Arctic area](#)' in the Spataneo Value chapter. In Google services you can even retrieve telephone numbers from the mobile phones browsing web sites, but on the server side, one only can see the internet addresses from the incoming traffic. These addresses can be pointed at distinct organizations based on internet databases, but getting persons is out of scope. Looking at the user distribution some companies and institutions could be identified from the users, while still a significant portion of users are private individuals as shown in

Figure 15 GetMap requests made to lake ice extend product divided into user groups on the left and with further analysis of the companies domains on the right (from thesis by Isabel Donner).

figure 15. Analysing further the company sectors, the information technology sector as a mediator is strong, but from the distribution also sees how many business sectors are interested. This information was used to identify who would be interviewed to further understand the interests of end-users and to be able to evaluate the value of the service for this sector.

But from the server side one can even better analyse the path that a user traverses the web site and based on this the user experience can be improved and made more convenient, because the smoother users find what they are looking for, the more likely they return. Also, the speed of delivery and service availability are important factors in this.

Promotion without marketing budgets

As marketing budgets are not included in Arctic PASSION, we used meaningful routes to promote our developments and by this also strengthened European capabilities in promoting our own services, as well as the use of Copernicus data. We have created websites for our services as the most important step overall. The [Arctic window](#) is showing all the services with their locations in figure 16 and the links in the following list:

- AS1 Event database of community-based monitoring <https://www.arcticseas.org/>

Figure 16 Arctic Passion Arctic window viewer showing the locations and areas covered by the Arctic passion services.

- AS2 Pan-Arctic permafrost (ALEX) <https://alex.awi.de/>
- AS3 State of the Arctic environment (soon to be launched)
- AS4 Fire Risk Management (INFRA) <https://www.programmicercaartico.it/integrated-fire-risk-management-infra-service>
- AS5 Local atmospheric pollutant forecast (AURORAE) <https://aurorae.azurewebsites.net/>
- AS6 Shipping safety <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/09ceaa10b3b34a3c83ec0380271d5162>
- AS7 Arctic marine climate change (to be launched)
- AS8 Arctic lake ice <https://testbed.ymparisto.fi/eo-tarkka/map/?ver=0&time=2024-05-30&style=opt&bbox=8.71238,57.40797,35.29569,64.71984&data=d-bm-esri,diceslstr&coll=cice&lang=en>

We have initiated also production chains to update the information on them to make users come back and refresh their knowledge. Furthermore, we promoted our websites and services in events and webinars in Europe and abroad including two big GEO events in Africa, GEO Global Forum in Rome and in the latest (2025) Arctic Science Summit Week in Boulder, Colorado. This will attract visits and hopefully carry the website address to continuous users as well. While due to the task mission, we targeted promoting European solutions to international parties, this promotion was also useful within Europe. Here the main venues were two EuroGEO workshops in Bolzano and Krakow. As a result of these exercises the services will also be registered in the GEO knowledge hub. On the EuroGEO website our services are being promoted under the [climate action group pages](#). Several services have also been presented in [Arctic GEOSS website](#) blog posts with more to come.

Conclusions to Strengthening European capabilities

As the conclusion of this report, European programmes and projects are recommended to be marketing their services on the internet. This would mean using some resources in projects to advertise on LinkedIn etc or improve search engine visibility by paying. It is however not only about marketing, but also about understanding the user base and giving it what it requested. Weather services that have a longer established web presence show how to track their success within the intended target group and how well this group is reached. In Finland more than five million inhabitants visiting a site over eleven million times equals to either everyone twice a month or some visiting more frequently, but this is a very good use. For the Arctic hub, it is unclear who and how many end users are targeted, so the 57 visits might also be achieving its targets, but this is not as clear. The second recommendation is to state clearly a mission and target for services. This would allow a clearer analysis of its success.

The approach to open data and solutions and collaborating widely is the basis of the success of Copernicus services, because they do already attract so much traffic with hundreds of thousands of developers and users to visit. But to reach broader audiences beyond developers and scientists, more collaboration with media and more activation of discussions on social media are needed. A third recommendation could be offering journalists training for reporting on Copernicus topics. This has been successfully done at FMI for decades towards Finnish journalists reporting on climate change or the weather.

Trying to participate in social discourse in our fields is a trickier topic. Many scientists have been targeted and bullied on the internet. Social media is a broad field, so the point shouldn't be to be present everywhere, but to try to inform in all those discussions that are ignited by misinformation and which our quality assured data could help to correct. As this is not very attractive work for people, one option would be to code AI agents to follow topical internet discussions and direct the discourse to check Copernicus information for quality input. This might also find new ways for reaching the public. Facebook has lost a lot of its active users in recent years and especially discussion and commenting have reduced by about 30% on the platform from its most active days in 2020. So, the sites are shifting and especially AI interaction could become the best avenue to ingest information from Copernicus services. ChatGPT is already hugely popular, and it is already generating traffic to some Copernicus services. Maybe this avenue could be broadened. Recommendation four would be, to at least monitor crawlers on Copernicus sites, so their resulting traffic in AI sites can be understood and maybe later directed.

In summary, the basic operation needs to continue with continuous quality data and information production. The dissemination practice needs to continue with open and free data policies, and we need to add more efforts for marketing our information. This can be paid traffic, or we could work closer with media and act more in social discourse.

ANNEX

Figure 17 Comparing site performance of data subdomains of Copernicus services (similarweb.com accessed 27.4.2025).

